

Research

Credit Risk Management effect on loan portfolio of any private Commercial Bank of Bangladesh

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Accepted: 22 December, 2020; Online: 25 December, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4393745>

Abstract: *As the competition is increasing, all the private commercial banks are constantly looking for scope to develop credit operation and performance appraisal to the market. However tight control on the part of the Central bank, Bangladesh Bank restricts the scope for maneuvering in the market with new performance and credit risk management on loan portfolio operation. Therefore banks require finding out untapped market space for growth. Moreover, in this loan portfolio crunch time, it is crucial for any private banks to be able to perform efficiently and effectively. In that case if the bank is not being able to perform than the bank might go bankrupt which would have a significant impact on the economy of Bangladesh. The aim of this paper is to analyze the performance of the loan portfolio of a private bank and also its credit policies which would show how the private commercial banks of Bangladesh lends to different kinds of clients. The paper also highlights how effective is the loan recovery system of the respective private bank. Findings revealed that the risk in case of account opening for loan purpose and for that find out the detail information of various clients and its verification process, also give an overview of the capacity of any private banks concern about its several areas of credit management, efficiency of following Bangladesh bank guidelines according to credit risk management.*

Keywords: *Credit Operation and performance, Credit Risk Management, Loan Portfolio operation, Impact on the economy of Bangladesh, Credit Policies, Loan recovery system.*

Introduction

Credit risk is one of the most vital risks for any private commercial bank .Credit risk arises from nonperformance by a borrower.

Anderson (2013, 292) defines credit risk as “the probability that a legally enforceable contract may become worthless (or at least substantially reduced in value) because the counterparty defaults and goes out of business.”

It may arise from either an inability or an unwillingness to perform in the pre-commitment contracted manner. The real risk of credit is the deviation of portfolio performance from its expected value. The credit risk of any bank is also has effect in its book value. The more credit of a particular is in risk, the more probability of a bank to be insolvent .Therefore, the status of depositor in the bank is at risk and probability of incurring loss from their deposited value. In other way the risk of any commercial bank is calculated through long and short term rating by the credit rating agencies.

For Most banks, loans account for half or more of their total assets and about two-thirds of their revenues. Moreover risk in banking tends to be concentrated in the loan portfolio. When a bank gets into serious financial trouble, its problem usually springs from loans that have become uncollectable due to mismanagement, illegal manipulation of loans, misguided lending policies or an unexpected economic downturn. So it is highly essential for any bank to maintain an effective management structure of for its credit risk that has a huge impact on banks performance and financial condition.

Credit risk is an important type of risk for any financial institution such as bank and it is often regarded as the oldest type of risk in financial markets dating back to 1800 BCE, the ancient Egyptian times (caouette, Altman and Narayan 2008). So the importance of this paper is to allow us to gaining knowledge about lending policies and procedures of any private commercial banks of Bangladesh and help us to understand how the loan portfolio of any specific private commercial bank is performing in comparison with other banks.

The principal reason banks and any other financial institutions are chartered by state and federal authorities is to make loans to their customers. The objective of financial institutions is to maximize profit and shareholder value-added by providing different financial services mainly by managing risks (Khan and Ahmad, 2001). Banks are accepted to support their local communities with an adequate supply of credit for all legitimate business and consumer activities and to price that credit reasonably in line with competitively determined interest rates. Indeed, making loans is

the principal economic function of banks-to fund consumption and investment spending by businesses, individuals and units of government. In formulating a credit judgment and making Quality credit decisions the lending officer must be equipped with all information needed to evaluate a borrower's character, management competence, capacity, capital, ability to provide collaterals and external conditions which may affect his ability in meeting financial obligations. Banks and similar financial institutions need to meet forthcoming regulatory requirements for risk measurement and capital. However, it is a serious error to think that meeting regulatory requirements is the sole or even the most important reason for establishing a sound, scientific risk management system. Managers need reliable risk measures to direct capital to activities with the best risk/reward ratios. They need estimates of the size of potential losses to stay within limits imposed by readily available liquidity, by creditors, customers, and regulators. They need mechanisms to monitor positions and create incentives for prudent risk-taking by divisions and individuals (Pyle, 1997). For the sake of sound lending, it is necessary to develop a sound policy and modern lending techniques have to be adopted to ensure that loans/advances are safe and the money will come back within the time set for repayment. For this purpose, proper and prior analysis of credit proposals is required to assess the risk. Lending itself is risky and the very purpose of analyzing the risk is to locate /identify the risk obtaining possible precaution. While deciding a loan proposal one is to judge the degree of risk in a given situation. Banker's ability in taking prior measures to minimize the risk involved is very important. To do this a bank must follow this principles of Sound Lending: Safety, Security, Purpose, Profitability, liquidity, diversification and national interest. Risk measurement deals with quantification of risk exposures, whereas risk management refers to the overall process by which managers satisfy these needs and follows to define a business strategy, to identify the risks to which it is exposed, to quantify those risks, and to understand and control the nature of risks it faces (Cumming and Beverly, 2001). Credit risk management maximizes bank's risk adjusted rate of return by maintaining credit risk exposure within acceptable limit in order to provide framework for understanding the impact of credit risk management on banks' profitability (Kargi, 2011). In that Case the main source of credit risk include, limited institutional capacity, inappropriate credit policies, volatile interest rates, poor management, inappropriate laws, low capital and liquidity levels, direct lending, massive licensing of banks, poor loan underwriting, laxity in credit assessment, poor lending practices, government interference and inadequate supervision by the central bank (Kithinji, 2010).

Materials and methods

Southeast Bank Capital Services Ltd. (SEBCSL) is a subsidiary of Southeast Bank Limited (SEBL or the Bank). SEBL obtained Merchant Banking License from Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC) to operate merchant banking activities on April 06, 2009. It started commercial operation from August 17, 2009. In compliance with legal provisions and regulatory requirements, SEBCSL was formed as a public limited company on September 23, 2010 to continue providing merchant banking services. Authorized Capital of the Company is Tk 6.00 billion and paid up capital is Tk 5.50 billion out of which Tk 5.48 billion was contributed by the bank, holding company. It is a highly capitalized merchant banking company. The services that the company provides are Portfolio Management, Underwriting to the IPO and Rights Issue, Issue Management Services, Corporate Advisory Services, etc. Southeast Bank Limited currently has approximately 30 people working in the credit department of the head office, which is the head of all the branches and from where all the credit facilities given to the clients are sanctioned and monitored. The credit division is headed by an Executive Vice President and two Vice Presidents under whom all the other staffs of the credit department holding different positions are working. Each and every work in the credit division is properly distributed to the subordinate staffs and it is possible because the work in the credit division is very systematic.

From the findings of different studies, it can be noted that at the very outset the banking sector in Bangladesh provided huge amount of soft debt facilities to trade, industry and farming activities for enhancing overall economic growth of the country and it was done as a part of social commitment of the nationalized sector. The Credit Division of Southeast Bank limited is divided in two parts. (i) General Credit which consists the functions of analysis of proposals for approval of credit committee, prepare for broad memo , communication and sanction advice and also prepare and submit of periodical returns of Bangladesh Bank and (ii) Corporate Finance which have the specific function of corporate credit proposal data evaluation, processing credit proposals for approval of credit committee, preparation of credit information memo (CIM) for Board and finally communication of sanction advice.

To compete with the current huge competition among all the Private and Government commercial banks, the Southeast Bank Limited offers different types of credit facilities that categories under

two different types of facilities: (1) Funded credit Facility that contain loans, several overdraft, Bills under L/C (BLC), Loan against imported merchandise (LIM), Trust Receipt (TR), Packing Credit and (2) Non Funded credit Facility which consist Letter of Credit (L/C), Bank Guarantee.

The research is based on theoretical methodology. To know the effect of credit risk management on loan portfolio of any private bank of Bangladesh, we focused and analyzed a specific private commercial bank of Bangladesh named Southeast Bank LTD. Both Primary and secondary sources of data were used towards the completion of this paper. The main primary source of data was the interview with the different level of employees in the credit department of the Head office of Southeast Bank Limited. Relevant files study that were provided by the officers concerned with credit department were also used.

Secondary data were mainly used for the completion of this paper. Some of the secondary data that were used are –

- Annual Report of Southeast Bank Limited.
- Several Articles and research Papers.
- Credit policy Guide (SEBL)
- Credit Operation Manual (SEBL)
- Books, Magazines etc. were also used.

Result

Performance Analysis of the credit portfolio of SEBL

Performance Analysis of the credit portfolio is completely based on the data of sector wise performance of the loan and its sector wise recovery. 8 (Felix and Claudine 2008) investigated the relationship between bank performance and credit risk management. It could be inferred from their findings that return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA) both measuring profitability were inversely related to the ratio of non-performing loan to total loan of financial institutions thereby leading to a decline in profitability. (Ahmad and Ariff 2007) examined the key determinants of credit risk of commercial banks on emerging economy banking systems compared with the developed economies. The study found that regulation is important for banking systems that offer

multi-products and services; management quality is critical in the cases of loan-dominant banks in emerging economies. Southeast Bank Limited offers a number of loans in various forms to its customers like demand loans, time loans, term loans, consumer credit scheme, BLC, LIM and etc.

Time Loan: Time loan is one of the most important parts of the credit portfolio of any bank that contributes quite a lot to the bank. Southeast Bank Limited also has a pretty healthy term loan position.

The position of the recovery of this loan is pretty stable and it is rising at a good rate because of SEBL give a constant monitoring in this sector of loan and its recovery procedure.

Term Loan: Term loan is the second most important and highest percentage of the total loan portfolio of Southeast Bank Limited. It nearly holds 24.5 percent of the total credit portfolio of SEBL. It is rising every year in a stable manner and the growth rate of this loan is approximately 46 percent.

Although the recovery of term loan is very slow but it is gradually increasing due to good loan recovery management present in Southeast bank limited. For the last four the recovery is taking place in a stable manner with uniform growth which is a good sign as recovery of term loan is not very easy and default is very much in this sector. But it is the characteristics of long-term loan that recovery will be a very slow process. On an average the total recovery of term loan in each year is about Tk. 635 million. This recovery is quite good if compared with the industry.

Working Capital Loan: SEBL has been encouraging in giving working capital loan in recent times as it is generally of short nature and the default nature is low in this case. It can be seen that the percentage of Working Capital Loan of the total credit portfolio is increasing gradually.

In case of recovery it is begin to recover the loan given in this sector is increasing. But if compared with the industry, its recovery is slow because the industry has an average recovery. One reason for this must be also that the demand for working Capital Loan in recent times is very high and every bank is trying to provide working Capital Loan. And this is the major concerned for the management of SEBL.

Commercial Credit: The credit that every bank provides the most and which brings the highest income is the commercial credit. This is the most because the demand for commercial credit is the highest among the entire loans. SEBL's highest percentage of loan amount all the credits is commercial loan which on an average is approximately 63 percent of the total loan. It comprises of more than half of the total portfolio. The industry also has approximately 50-65 percent of its loan concentrated towards different types of commercial loans.

As the commercial credit comprises of the majority amount of loan in the total loan portfolio and is most important as it gives the highest earnings so its recovery is also very important because classified loan is most in this sector in SEBL. The commercial loan recovery is increasing in a good speed although there are defaults. On an average the recovery of commercial loan every year is close to Tk.2550 million, whereas the industry has a recovery of approximately Tk.2200-2800 million on an average. So SEBL is within the industry line.

Large And Medium Scale Industrial Loan: This loan consists of the entire loan that comprises of the long-term project loan like infrastructure, building, factory etc.

This is the type of loan that SEBL has not given in large quantity because of the default nature of this type of loan and the problem of recovery. But even then the amount of money that has been given in this loan is quite large as each investment carries huge amount of investment. On an average the percentage of term loan given away is approximately 11percent of the total loan portfolio. Other Private commercial Bank (PCB) percentage of term loan is approximately 15percent of the total portfolio which shows that SEBL is in the lower side and this is one reason why its classified loan is low.

Export Credit: SEBL has been offering export credit from the beginning and it didn't vary much during from the start of its business. On an average, it has been giving approximately 1.5 percent of the total credit in export finance. Export credit has always been the priority of some of the nationalized banks in Bangladesh along with some first generation banks. But recent trends show that export credit has been going down for some times and the reason may be that the world business environment is not very stable due to current pandemic.

Small And Cottage Industry: This sector in Bangladesh is not very prominent and still in the growing phase. SEBL in comparison with the industry has only 0.03 percent of the loan concentrated to this sector which is the lowest among all the credit offered.

In case of recovery as the percentage of loan allocated in this sector is very nominal, the recovery is also very small and another reason behind the little recovery is that SEBL doesn't concentrate much in this sector. The average recovery of loan in this sector is about Tk.0.89 million per year.

The Portfolio Analysis: The portfolio analysis shows that SEBL has a stable credit rating ratio. The credit rating Information And Services Limited (CRISL) has reaffirmed the long term rating of Southeast Bank Limited at AA (Pronounced as Double A) and the short term rating at ST -2 based on audited financials up to 31st December, 2019 and unaudited financials up to 31st March, 2020 and other relevant qualitative as well as quantitative information up to the date of rating.

Credit Rating	2018	2019
Long Term	AA	AA
Short Term	ST-2	ST-2

Date of Rating: July 29, 2020.

Validity: Up to July 28, 2021.

Explanation:

The bank rated AA (High Safety) in credit rating is adjusted to be of high quality, offers higher safety and has high credit quality. This level of credit rating indicates corporate entity with a sound credit profile and without significant problems. Risks are modest and may vary slightly from time to time because of economic conditions.

The bank rated ST-2 (High Grade) in the short term in credit rating is considered to have high certainty of timely payment .Liquidity factors are strong and supported by good fundamental protection factors. Risks factors are very small.

Discussion

Credit Risk Management (CRM) Strategies of Southeast Bank LTD

The credit policy of any banking institution is a combination of certain accepted, time tested standards and other dynamic factors dictated by the realities of changing situations in different market places. According to (Lindergren 1987), the key principles in credit risk management process are sequenced as follows; establishment of a clear structure, allocation of responsibility, processes have to be prioritized and disciplined, responsibilities should be clearly communicated and accountability assigned. The credit risk management strategies of SEBL according to results are profitability focused and are accepted standards relate to safety, liquidity and profitability of the advance whereas the dynamic factors relate to aspects such as the nature and extent of risk, interest on margin, credit spread and credit dispersal and we can point it out below:

Credit Risk Evaluation: An accurate appraisal of risk in any credit exposure is highly subjective matter involving quantitative and qualitative judgments. The financial statements of the borrower do not always provide a complete picture. Concerning about it as like all other commercial bank SEBL must use all financial data available and combine this with qualitative factors in analyzing the borrower's financial position. In evaluating any credit proposal, the analyst must follow THREE distinct and logical steps to conclude on and make appropriate recommendations. These are: 1. Historical Analysis (Identify Nature of risk), 2. Forecast (Judging future degree of risk) and 3. Debt structure and protection.

Credit Risk Management- Lending Decision: To safeguard SEBL's interest over the entire period of the advance, a comprehensive view of the capital, capacity, integrity of the borrower, adequacy, nature of security, compliance with all legal formalities, completion of all documentation and finally a constant watch on the account are called for. Where advances are granted against the guarantee of a third party, that guarantor must be subjected to the same credit assessment as made for the principal borrower. The basic security valuations will be expert third party assessments,

current market price and forced sale value. While making lending decisions, particular attention should be given to the analysis of credit proposals received from heavily leveraged companies and those dealings in non-essential consumer goods, taking special care about their debt servicing abilities.

Compliance to BASEL Accord: The Basel Accord are international principles and regulations guiding the operations of banks to ensure soundness and stability. Bangladesh Bank, the prime supervisory authority of the financial sector implemented the new capital standard – Basel II from January 2009 in parallel with Basel I. From January 01, 2010 Basel II has been solely implemented in the banking sector. Basel II requires addressing and managing the market risk and operational risk in addition to the existing (as per Basel I) credit risk. Basel II capital standard is acting as a major catalyst for enrichment of risk management practices within the bank embedding the risk culture in the bank's operation. In response to the new capital accord (Basel II), risk management process within the bank has been introduced supporting the principles of more risk sensitive approach to capital adequacy which is helpful enough to follow by SEBL.

Lending Policy Adoption of SEBL: Concept of lending pre-supposes a well-developed loan proposal. It will cover as many as six pertinent factors like Management, Organizational, Technical, Marketing, Financial and Economical. These are technically known as feasibility or viability study of a loan proposal. By studying all these factors if a credit officer of bank is satisfied about the viability of a loan proposal, then he/she can finance it i.e. grant for lending otherwise not.

The Credit Team: This team's general guidelines about the conduct of advances are issued by Head Office. In all credit dealings, officers and employees must be guided by the principles of honesty, integrity and safeguard the interest of the depositors and shareholders of the Bank. They should strictly adhere to the Banking Laws, Rules and Regulations of the Government of Bangladesh, the instructions issued by Bangladesh Bank/Head Office from time to time which affect the business practices of the Bank.

Documentations Against Bank Credit: Documentation is one of the major aspects of credit functions of Southeast Bank Limited as like other private commercial banks of

Bangladesh. Documentation is the written statement of facts or evidence in regard to a particular transaction, which on placement may bind the parties answerable and liable to the court of law. Documentation formalities against loans and advances should be properly completed prior to extension of the facility to safeguard the Bank's interest. Complete and correct documentation enables the credit officer of SEBL to take legal resource against the borrower in case of non-realization of dues.

Management of Noncompliance Act for Any Penalty: According to the guideline "if a bank's employee willfully/knowingly furnishes false information in reporting to Bangladesh Bank, such an offence is punishable under section 109(2) of the Bank Company Ain 1991. Bangladesh Bank may impose penalty as per section 109(7) of the said Ain if a bank fails to submit the above mentioned reports within stipulated time without any acceptable/satisfactory reason." So SEBL have a strong committee to meet up this sort of issues of noncompliance.

Recommendations

Southeast Bank Ltd. is one of the potential banks in the banking sector in Bangladesh. In that case most of the parties involved in bank-dealings suffer from the following limitations: 1) lack of proper identification of the determinants related to bank dealings, 2) failure to properly identifying risks involved in banking transaction; and 3) lack of knowledge to manage the risks faced by banks. All these necessity call for an in-depth investigation on risk management practices and here lies the justification of this study. The recommendations given below are not decisions; rather they are only individual perspectives to improve the customer's service in order to fulfill the customer's satisfaction so that customers give more preference to SEBL. The recommendations are given below:

1. Develop more customized parameters for credit management.
2. Bank can encourage business loan nearby consumer loan that will be helpful for the economy by increasing investment.
3. The SEBL may encourage female entrepreneurs to take loan that will directly affect the social economy of our country and it will help to strengthen our economy.
4. Term loan should be encouraged so that businessman's can take this loan easily.

5. Emphasis should be given on promotion to create a strong brand value, in today's world there is no alternative to promote your brand.
6. SEBL should diversify its lending sector to reduce the risk of defaulting.
7. It is important to identify challenges and vulnerabilities and be transparent with the regulatory authority for adequate policy support in due time.

Conclusion

Banking is the backbone of national economy. Banking sector no more depends on only on a traditional method of banking. Banking industry has been treated as a prospective financial sector in Bangladesh. Presently, Bangladesh's banking system is deeply affected by bad loans. This is not only disrupting the lending system, it discourages investment. As a result the growth of the economy is being hampered. In general because of risk management is expensive; it involves extra effort, monetary cost or opportunity cost. Risk management is particularly crucial in banks and financial institutions that handle deposits of the common people. In a bank, risks are handled within stringent regulatory and compliance framework. At present Covid-19 has brought a comprehensive risk environment in our personal, economic and social lives. Economic and business disruptions have started to affect banking industry throughout the globe. Banks in Bangladesh are also facing huge uncertainties and skepticism especially about repayments of loans by their clients when their business are in disarray. In the pre-covid-19 situation, some banks of the country were already struggling with non-performing loans. The current situation might bring huge burden of non-performing loans for the banking industry if the growing credit risk in this Covid-19 environment is not addressed effectively. With changing time Bangladesh bank has set rules and general guidelines to help banks asses risk and mitigate their credit risk. Hence, it is not only the guidance provided by the Bangladesh bank in sufficient but also a commercial lending institution need to follow own lending policies should be in place to ensure maximum effectiveness of credit assessment. banks must take due preparation as part of their Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) to accelerate economic recovery in the post-covid-19 situation where the board and top management have critical role to play to lead risk

management efforts. ERM framework in the banking industry is not present in the most developing countries. As part of ERM, it is time that a contingency team should start working actively to gather data, monitor activities, update the board and top management and get ready for preparing a reliable situational analysis of the bank when needed. The contingency team may also help strategizing the effective use of the stimulus package to optimize benefits for the bank and clients. Strategic communications with the clients might be very effective at this stage to repair damage of clients' trusts and confidence, if any, and to handle the problem of moral hazard. Credit risk management is becoming more and more important in today's competitive business world. It is all the more important in the context of Bangladesh. The techniques of improving management of consumer credit risk have advanced considerably in the recent years. They have to be up to date in complying with all the required procedures and must employ competent and skilled manpower who have the ability to deal with these complex matters. SEBL has already developed goodwill among its client by offering excellent services. This success has been possible from the dedication, commitment and dynamic leadership of its management over the periods.

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Acknowledgments

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. I would like to acknowledge all the officials and staff of Southeast Bank as they for their huge cooperation. I also acknowledge department of human resource of the bank and all the branch member of Southeast Bank Limited, Mohammadpur Branch.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare in the preparation and presentation of the research report.

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